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“DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF PERCEPTUAL LEARNING MODULE IN QUADRATIC EQUATION AND SPECIAL PRODUCTS”

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ABSTRACT

Mathematics is the science of patterns, relationships and structure; it is the logical analysis, deduction and calculation contained by these patterns and structures. Module, as a self- instructional material, can be used as supplementary material to help improve students' performance. The use and application of appropriate teaching-learning tool such as learning module is necessary. A mathematics module that can motivate, self-directed, easy to understand, and perceptual in nature. In this study, perceptual learning module in the domain of patterns and algebra was developed. Specifically, consisted of lessons in Quadratic Equations and Special Products. The developmental research design was employed in the study, particularly, the ADDIE (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation and Evaluation) model on instructional material development was strictly followed. Respondents of the study included: 110 grade 8 students from Sara National High School, chosen purposively to answer the validated and reliability tested 30-item test, 20 mathematics teachers validated the initial draft of the lessons, 56 mathematics teachers evaluated the module. Results confirmed the teachers' assessments that students have not mastered even the basic concepts of quadratics and special products. This was made as a basis in the development of “I'M In (Intervention for Mathematics Instruction)” a Perceptual Learning Module. The module was rated “excellent by the

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teachers in terms of physical attributes, objectives, instructions, content, learning activities and evaluation. Meanwhile, the students' insights and experiences suggest positive attitude towards math learning, their performance increased significantly after exposure to the module. Thus, possible replication of the study to cover other topics for perceptual learning module is recommended.

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